

Tell Fekheriyeh Inscription

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Tell Fekheriyeh is an archeological site identified as the ancient city of Sikan (located in modern day Syria); an Aramean city thought to be an important cult site for the storm god Hadad. Sikan (and neighboring sites) fell under Neo-Assyrian control around the first half of the 9th century BCE. In February 1979, the Tell Fekheriyeh statue was discovered accidentally by a farmer in the southwest corner of Tell Fekheriyeh and today the statue stands at the National Museum of Damascus. Although the precise date of the statue is debated, most scholars agree the statue most likely dates around the late 9th or early 8th centuries BCE. The Tell Fekheriyeh statue was carved from basalt and depicts a life-size man, standing roughly 1.65 meters tall. Inscriptions on the statue identify the man as Had-Yithi, an Aramean governor/king. To the untrained eye (aka non-art historians) the iconography and style of the statue appears to be firmly Neo-Assyrian. While there are some strong connections between the styles, there are some distinct variations that differentiate the Tell Fekheriyeh statue from statues we find in the heart of the Neo-Assyrian Empire (compare the 9th century statues of Ashurnasirpal II and Shalmaneser III). The man at Tell Fekheriyeh is carved with curly shoulder-length hair and a long curly beard. He is wearing a short-sleeve tunic with a fringe shawl that comes over his left shoulder and tucks into a fringe belt at his waist. The bottom of his tunic is lined with a similar fringe on the hem. His feet are carved with incredible detail (down to the cuticle) and his sandals are tied neatly with thongs. His hands are empty but come together across his chest in a benedictory pose. Unlike 9th century Neo-Assyrian iconography, the man does not wear any jewelry nor a headdress, and his tunic lacks ornamentation. However, down the man's skirt is a lengthy bilingual inscription: an Akkadian text down the front, written in a vertical orientation, and an Old Aramaic translation written horizontally on the back. The Old Aramaic inscription is one of the oldest and most complete Aramaic texts, making it an invaluable resource for understanding the vocabulary, grammar, and syntax of the Old Aramaic language. The Akkadian inscription is also interesting, as this is the only example of a vertically oriented cuneiform text in the first millennium. The dress is completely covered in text from the fringe of the belt to the fringe of the hem. The genre of the inscription is understood as a dedicatory inscription that commemorates the dedication of the statue to the Aramean god, Hadad. Hadad was at the top of the Aramean pantheon and likely had a temple or cult center at Sikan. Hadad was a storm deity worshiped among various groups in both Mesopotamia (as Adad) and Syria since the second millennium BCE. The inscription suggests that Had-Yithi dedicated this statue to evoke the protection and blessing of Hadad over his life and his reign. The inscription also includes a lengthy list of curses against any who deface the statue or remove Had-Yithi's name from upon it. While the cultic (or religious) function of the statue is unknown, the dedication and curses suggest the statue may have been a votive statue, meant to stand in for Had-Yithi at a temple of Hadad. While much remains unknown about the actual function of the statue and its inscription, the statue itself embodies a blending of Assyrian and Aramean traditions that likely reflects the reality of 9th century Sikan.

Date Range: 890 BCE - 750 CE

Region: Tel Fekheriyeh (Sikan), Syria

Region tags: Syria

Sikan, located roughly 2 km from Tel Halaf (ancient Guzan) around the 9th century BCE

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Younger, K. Lawson. 2016. *A Political History of the Arameans: From Their Origins to the End of Their Polities*. Society of Biblical Literature, Archaeology, and Biblical Studies. Atlanta, GA: SBL Press
- Source 2: Crouch, Carly L., and Jeremy Michael Hutton. 2019. *Translating Empire: Tell Fekheriyeh, Deuteronomy, and the Akkadian Treaty Tradition*. Vol. 135. *Forschungen Zum Alten Testament* 135. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck.
- Source 3: Abou-Assaf, Ali, Pierre Bordreuil, and A. R. Millard. 1982. *La Statue de Tell Fekherye: Et Son Inscription Bilingue Assyro-Araméenne*. *Etudes Assyriologiques*. Paris: Sur Les Civilisations

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://virtual-museum-syria.org/damascus/statue-of-hadad-yithi-bearing-bilingual-inscription/>

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Incised or Inscribed

Method of inscription

- Other [specify]: Precise tool unknown, inscription carved into stone

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Stone

Notes: Basalt

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Notes: The stone was likely smoothed and carved into its current shape before the inscription was incised.

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: Unknown, the format of the inscription (double introduction) have led some scholars to hypothesize that the inscription was once shorter and inscribed on a different statue before being transferred and extended on the Tel Fekheriyeh statue. There is no way to know for sure.

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Based on similar statues found in the Neo Assyrian period, it is likely the statue was located in a temple or cult setting. However, the statue itself was not found in its original context, so we do not know for sure.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Yes

Notes: Both the iconography of the statue and the text itself suggest that the statue was commissioned by the local political authority at Sikan. The text indicates the statue is meant to be a dedicatory or votive offering to the god Hadad to secure Had-Yithi a prosperous reign, and thus the statue would have served both political and cultic functions. However, the political, cultic, and economic apparatus that would have supported the commission of such a statue is unknown.

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Notes: The commissioner of this statue is named as Had-Yithi the governor/King of Guzan. It is likely that he funded the creation of the statue as well as the composition of the text.

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– No

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Likely the local population at Sikan as well as Neo-Assyrian diplomats.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: If the statue did indeed function as a votive statue and stand in a temple, it likely would have had a "magical" or apotropaic function where it served to evoke the blessing of Hadad on Had-Yithi's life and reign. There may have been ritual practices surrounding the creation and installation of the statue, but we cannot know for sure.

Is there material significance to the text?

– Yes

↳ Is it visible?

– Yes

Notes: The text is displayed prominently, covering the entire skirt of the statue.

↳ Is it hidden?

– No

↳ Can it be touched?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Statue may have stood on a pedestal, out of the reach of the viewers. But again, this is largely unknown.

↳ Does touching the text during ritual have a specific function?

– No

↳ Does the material significance have an esoteric function?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Depending on the literacy at Sikan, it is likely only a very small group could have actually read either (or both) the Aramaic and Akkadian inscriptions. Moreover, the vertical orientation of the Akkadian and the position of the Aramaic on the back of the statue would have made it difficult to read even for a literate audience. It is worth noting that texts on monumental statues such as the Tel Fekheriyeh statue communicated in more ways than they're being read. Audiences were likely aware of the longstanding tradition of Akkadian as a language and script of monumental architecture. Similarly, audiences would have likely recognized their local aramean script, even if they could not read the text. The presence of text on the statue of Had-Yithi likely communicated something to the ancient audience that remains lost to modern

audiences.

↳ Does the text serve a protective function?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text appears to evoke the blessing of Hadad, suggesting that it serves to protect Had-Yithi.

↳ Does the text serve a healing function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve a cleansing function?

– No

↳ Does the text serve as a form of expiation?

– No

↳ Does the text serve as an incantation?

– No

↳ Has the materiality of the text been altered?

– No

↳ Are there debates about whether or not altering the materiality of the text is acceptable?

– No

↳ Other important aspects of materiality with regard to the text?

– No

↳ Are there material substance that commonly accompany the text?

Please specify the substances in the sub-questions

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Yes

Notes: The text is accompanied by the iconography of the statue on which the text is inscribed. The meaning of the text then, must be considered alongside the iconography of the statue itself.

↳ Calligraphy?

– No

↳ Illustrations?

– No

↳ Illuminations?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: The text is stand-alone, but is part of a broader literary tradition of kings inscribing texts on images of themselves or their gods in order to evoke the blessing of their god. These texts also serve political purposes, functioning to validate and promote the king's political ideology and prominence.

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: Text includes divine epithets for Hadad and lists of blessings and curses

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: The text claims Had-Yithi is the son of Shash-nuri, King of Guzan. This information is vague, but scholars have used this brief lineage in attempts to date the text.

↳ Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

↳ How is the lineage established?

– Blood or Marriage relations

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

Notes: Hadad is a storm deity and in this text, one associated with regulating the waters of the sky and earth.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Notes: There is no formal theology known about the Aramaean worship of Hadad. Based on this text, Hadad appears to have control over the weather and the availability and prosperity of the land. Hadad also appears to have some level of control over Had-Yithi's personal well being and the success of his reign. Hadad also appears able to curse or harm those who desecrate the statue.

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Has other knowledge of this world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world
 - Yes
- ↳ Can reward
 - Yes
- ↳ Can punish
 - Yes
- ↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Exhibits positive emotion
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Exhibits negative emotion
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Possesses Hunger?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can be hurt?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can be tricked?
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Can be imprisoned?
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

Notes: Hadad was considered to be the top deity over a divine council or pantheon of other deities.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Communication of Hadad to the people/Had-Yithi is not discussed in this text.

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The text suggests Had-Yithi's ability to communicate with the god, but the text itself does not enable communication with the divine.

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: The text is focused on Hadad, but based on other Aramaic and Akkadian texts we know he existed within a pantheon of other deities.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Again, this depends on the function of the text, which we can only speculate. The text certainly suggests the presence of Hadad's blessing and cursing, but it is unknown whether the audience of the text would have considered the deity physically present in/around the object. My inclination is no, since the statue itself is of Had-Yithi, not Hadad.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Notes: The god Hadad is evoked in the text, but Hadad is not depicted as monitoring or requiring any particular behaviors or beliefs. In this text, the god is evoked as a means of protection and blessing on Had-Yithi.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: The punishment of the deity is called upon in the curse section, if in the future anyone desecrates the statue or removes Had-Yithi's name from upon it.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: Again, the protection of the deity is called upon in the text, but the text itself does not depict or guarantee any reward.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Notes: While the text does not proscribe sacrifices, offerings, or sacred space, the text does list curses against anyone who defects the statue or removes Had-Yithi's name from upon it. This suggests that the maintenance of the statue itself - its physical integrity and Had-Yithi's name on it - was necessary for receiving Hadad's blessing.

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: Sikan was part of a larger Aramean polity with Guzan as its capitol city. This polity was likely

under the control (although the degree to which is largely unknown) of the Neo Assyrian empire at the time of the statue's creation and composition.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: We have no other copies of the text to suggest it was ever reproduced.

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: The statue itself shows signs of being defaced (the statue was found without its head, and the head was found missing a nose) but the text itself was never defaced. It remains remarkably preserved. Those responsible for breaking the statue are unknown.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Notes: The text is not concerned with welfare. It is concerned with the successful and prosperous reign of Had-Yithi.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Field doesn't know

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Tell Fekheriyeh Inscription, Younger, K. Lawson. *A Political History of the Arameans : From Their Origins to the End of Their Polities*. Atlanta, GA: Society of Biblical Literature Press, 2016.

Reference: Tell Fekheriyeh Inscription, Crouch, Carly L., and Jeremy Michael Hutton. *Translating Empire : Tell Fekheriyeh, Deuteronomy, and the Akkadian Treaty Tradition*. *Forschungen Zum Alten Testament* 135. Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2019.

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